

Comparison Of Two Different Platelet-Rich Fibrin Membranes to Improve Peri-Implant Mucosa Thickness

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ABSTRACT

Objective: The aim of present study was to compare the efficiency of PRF membrane vs Ascorbic Acid- PRF membrane in improving peri implant mucosa thickness around immediate implants. **Method:** A total of 16 sites were split into two groups ie, Group L-PRF included 8 sites indicated for immediate implant placement along with L-PRF membrane and Group AA-PRF included 8 sites indicated for immediate implant placement along with AA-PRF membrane placement. The clinical parameters assessed included Wound healing index (Landry, Turnbull, Howley,1988), Keratinised Tissue Width (KMW), Mucosal Thickness (MT) And Crestal Bone Level (mesial and distal). **results:** From baseline to 3 months, the increase in the keratinized tissue width was significantly greater in the AA-PRF group than in the L-PRF group. At 3 months, increase in the mucosal thickness and crestal bone level was greater in the AA-PRF group than the L-PRF group but it was statistically non-significant. Intragroup comparison was statistically significant for keratinized tissue width, mucosal thickness and peri-implant bone thickness for both groups. **Conclusion:** It was inferred that, although both interventions showed improvements in clinical and radiographic outcomes 3 months post-surgically, augmenting PRF with Ascorbic Acid resulted in significant improvement in quality of peri-implant tissues.

Keywords: PRF membrane, ascorbic acid, dental implants, immediate implant.

INTRODUCTION

Since the inception of dentistry, various concepts have been suggested out of which implants have emerged as a revolutionary idea. Since **Branemark** introduced the first titanium dental implant in 1965, multiple techniques have been tried and tested with time. In 1996, **Lindhe and Berglundh** [1] suggested that the thickness of keratinized mucosa has a role to play in the stability of bone around the implant. With this study, the significance of soft tissue thickness to protect marginal bone was established. Like the periodontal phenotype, the peri-implant phenotype may undergo remodelling with time according to the available environmental factors. [2]

Puisys et al. [3] in his study to evaluate crestal bone stability after using allogenic membrane to improve thin mucosal tissues around implants found out that augmentation of thin soft tissues with membrane during implant placement improved peri-implant phenotype as well as reduce crestal bone loss.

Various methods like using autologous grafts, xenogenic membranes, porcine dermal matrix or tenting screws, etc have been used in the past to improve peri-implant soft tissue thickness. Lately, membranes are considered as a viable approach of local remodelling to influence the quality of tissues around implants. The addition of antibiotics agents like tetracycline, clindamycin, etc; to the blood while preparing PRF may provide with local benefits. Using PRF infused with antibiotics, titanium, etc; in surgical sites may reduce the risk of post-operative infection due to the healing properties of PRF. [4] They are a rich source of the growth factors which is what enhances the tissue's natural healing capacity. [5] Consequently, the addition of biomolecules like Ascorbic acid to platelet-rich fibrin (PRF) may elicit a positive response on periodontal health around the implant. Previously, administration of Ascorbic acid has shown to improve periodontal disease. It has shown to proliferate and differentiate mesenchymal stem cells of the periodontium. A study done by **Elbehwashy et al** [7] to assess platelet-rich fibrin

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(PRF) with ascorbic acid versus PRF in intra-osseous defects of stage-III periodontitis patients showed supplementing PRF with AA could additionally augment radiographic linear defect fill and reduce gingival recession depth. Hence, the aim of this study is to assess the effect of L-PRF vs Ascorbic Acid- PRF membrane on peri-implant mucosal thickness, crestal bone levels and healing around implants.

MATERIALS & METHOD

The study was conducted on patients selected from the outpatient Department of Periodontology and Oral Implantology, I.T.S Centre for Dental Studies and Research, Muradnagar, Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh, India. The study was conducted for a duration of 8 months ie, from November 2023 to June 2024. All participants have read and signed informed consent form. It was a randomised controlled trial where a total of 16 sites indicated for immediate implant placement were selected. The first group was L-PRF group which included 8 patients indicated for immediate implant placement along with PRF membrane followed by 8 patients indicated for immediate implant placement along with AA-PRF membrane placement. The study was sanctioned by I.T.S institutional ethics committee (IIEC).

The inclusion criteria included any patients aged 18+ who required an immediate implant with adequate quantity of bone and adequate interocclusal height and with peri-implant phenotype ≤ 2 mm. Patients with adequate oral hygiene status and no active periodontal disease.

Any patients with a history of severe periodontitis. Smokers, uncontrolled systemic diseases, pregnant and lactating women were excluded from the study.

PRF Preparation

L-PRF: For PRF preparation, 10mL of blood sample was collected into a blood collection tube without anticoagulant, which was immediately subject to

centrifugation at 2,700 rpm (around 400g) for 12min. The obtained PRF is usually termed as Choukroun's PRF or leukocyte and PRF (L-PRF).

AA-PRF: For AA-PRF preparation, 10 mL of fresh blood was collected into a blood collection tube without anticoagulant. In the AA-PRF group, 2500 μ g pure AA was added to the fresh blood to achieve a concentration of 250 μ g/ml AA and the tube was centrifuged at 3000rpm(400g) for 10 min at room temperature. ⁽⁵⁾

FIG 1 : AA-PRF MEMBRANE :

Surgical phase

The surgical site was prepared using chlorhexidine mouth rinse for 30 seconds. Following local anesthesia administration at the site of operation, atraumatic extraction was performed. Followed by irrigating the socket, the implant was then placed into the osteotomy site prepared. Before closing the flap, freshly centrifuged PRF membrane was placed over the implant and sutured using 4- 0 vicryl. Following which IOPA in paralleling technique was taken immediately after.

Fig 2: surgical procedure: a. Incision b. PRF placement c. Suture d. 2 weeks post op

At 7 days and 14 days, Landry's wound healing index was recorded for both, group L-PRF and group AA-PRF. Also, the keratinised tissue width, mucosal thickness and crestal bone levels were assessed at baseline and at 3 months.

Keratinised tissue width and mucosal thickness were measured using a William's probe and a K-file respectively. A stent was used to standardise the measurement. Crestal bone levels were measured from a line drawn from CEJ of adjacent teeth till the neck of implant using IOPA taken in standardised paralleling technique.

Fig 3 : Mucosal Thickness And Keratinised Tissue Width At Baseline And 3 Months (L-Prf Group)

Fig 4 : Mucosal Thickness And Keratinised Tissue Width At Baseline And 3 Months (L-Prf Group)

Fig 5 : Iopa At Baseline And 3 Months (L-Prf And Aa-Prf Group Respectively)

Statistical analysis

The received data was assessed using SPSS software v 23.0. The level of significance was kept at 5%. Demographic and clinical characteristics were presented using descriptive statistics and compared using an independent t-test or chi-square test depending on the nature of the data. A comparison of baseline and 3 months for keratinised tissue width, mucosal thickness and crestal bone levels were assessed for both groups using Mann Whitney test.

RESULT

The mean age of the study subjects of the L-PRF and AA-PRF groups was 49.75 years and 48.38 SD years respectively. Four males and three females were in the L-PRF group, whereas five males and one female were in the AA-PRF group. The demographic profile of the studied individuals is presented in **(Table 1)**.

Table 1: Demographic details

Variable	Category	L-PRF	AA-PRF
Age (in years)	--	49.75 ± 10.10	48.38 ± 13.80
Gender	Male	4 (57.14%)	5 (83.33%)
	Female	3 (42.85%)	1 (16.66%)

PRF: Leukocyte Platelet rich fibrin, AA-PRF: Ascorbic acid Platelet rich fibrin

Values are presented as mean±standard deviation.

The clinical parameters assessed included Wound healing index (Landry, Turnbull, Howley,1988), Keratinised Tissue Width (KMW), Mucosal Thickness (MT) And Crestal Bone Level on mesial and distal aspect of implant.

Both groups L-PRF and AA-PRF, although not significant, showed improvement in WHI score from day 7 to day 14. (Table 2)

Table 2 : Comparison of Landry's Wound Healing Index between two groups

Interval	Group	Mean ± SD	Median (IQR)	p-value
7 days	L-PRF	3.75 ± 1.04	4.00 (3.00)	0.180
	AA-PRF	3.00 ± 1.07	3.00 (2.00)	
14 days	L-PRF	4.50 ± 0.53	4.50 (1.00)	0.117
	AA-PRF	4.88 ± 0.35	5.00 (0.00)	

Mann Whitney test, a) Statistically significant difference compared to the baseline

Values are presented as mean±standard deviation.

On intergroup comparison from baseline to 3 months, there was a significant increase in the keratinized tissue width in AA-PRF group than in the L-PRF

group. At 3 months, increase in the mucosal thickness and crestal bone level was greater in the AA-PRF group than the L-PRF group but it was statistically non-significant. (Table 3,4)

Table 3: Intergroup comparison of keratinized tissue width and mucosal thickness between two groups

Variable	Interval	Group	Mean	SD	Difference	p-value
KTW	Baseline	L-PRF	5.25	1.67	1.00	0.083
		AA-PRF	4.25	0.46		
	3 months	L-PRF	6.38	1.28	-0.31	0.798
		AA-PRF	6.69	0.46		
	B-3months	L-PRF	1.13	0.69	-1.31	0.003 ^{a)}
		AA-PRF	2.44	0.62		
Mucosal Thickness	Baseline	L-PRF	1.44	0.50	-0.12	0.645
		AA-PRF	1.56	0.42		
	3 months	L-PRF	2.25	0.38	-0.56	0.010 ^{a)}
		AA-PRF	2.81	0.26		
	B-3months	L-PRF	0.81	0.59	-0.44	0.161
		AA-PRF	1.25	0.27		

Mann Whitney test; a) Statistically significant difference compared to the baseline

Table 4: Intragroup comparison of keratinized tissue width and mucosal thickness between two groups

Variable	Group	Baseline		3 months		Difference	p-value
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
KTW	L-PRF	5.25	1.67	6.38	1.28	-1.13	0.017 ^{a)}
	AA-PRF	4.25	0.46	6.69	0.46	-2.34	0.010 ^{a)}
Mucosal thickness	L-PRF	1.44	0.5	2.25	0.38	-0.71	0.026 ^{a)}
	AA-PRF	1.56	0.42	2.81	0.26	-1.25	0.010 ^{a)}

Wilcoxon signed rank test; a) Statistically significant difference compared to the baseline

On intragroup comparison, Keratinized tissue width and mucosal thickness after 3 months was significantly greater than the baseline keratinized tissue width in both the groups. On the mesial side, the peri-implant bone thickness after 3 months was

significantly greater than the baseline peri-implant bone thickness in each group. However, on the distal side, the peri-implant bone thickness after 3 months was significantly greater than the baseline peri-implant bone thickness in AA-PRF group only. (Table 5,6)

Table 5: Intergroup comparison of Crestal Bone Level on the mesial and distal side between two groups

Variable	Interval	Group	Mean	SD	Difference	p-value
Mesial	Baseline	L-PRF	1.75	0.71	0.00	0.959
		AA-PRF	1.75	0.46		
	3 months	L-PRF	2.26	0.64	-0.30	0.328
		AA-PRF	2.56	0.42		
	B-3months	L-PRF	0.51	0.44	-0.44	0.328
		AA-PRF	0.81	0.59		
Distal	Baseline	L-PRF	1.50	0.71	0.00	0.878
		AA-PRF	1.50	0.54		
	3 months	L-PRF	1.75	0.85	-0.18	0.574
		AA-PRF	1.93	0.58		
	B-3months	L-PRF	0.25	0.38	-0.18	0.328
		AA-PRF	0.43	0.32		

Mann Whitney test; a) Statistically significant difference compared to the baseline

Table 6: Intragroup comparison of Crestal Bone Level on the mesial and distal side between two groups

Side	Group	Baseline		3 months		Difference	p-value
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Mesial	L-PRF	1.75	0.71	2.26	0.64	-0.51	0.026 ^{a)}
	AA-PRF	1.75	0.46	2.56	0.42	-0.81	0.016 ^{a)}
Distal	L-PRF	1.5	0.71	1.75	0.85	-0.25	0.102
	AA-PRF	1.5	0.54	1.93	0.58	-0.43	0.024 ^{a)}

Wilcoxon signed rank test; a) Statistically significant difference compared to the baseline

DISCUSSION

Immediate implants are proven to show satisfactory results when they osseointegrate well into the host

bone and bear occlusal stresses with an overall survival rate of 98.5%. [7] The benefits of immediate implants are lesser surgical procedures, shortened treatment time, patient compliance and preservation of hard and soft tissue contour. They also have disadvantages like presence of jumping gap may call for some augmentation during or after implant placement. Although, the approach for promoting complete soft tissue closure and treating the gap is debatable, various augmentation procedures such as autografts, bone substitutes and platelet-rich plasma has been employed. Platelet derivatives have come into limelight due to their regenerative capacity. [8] Clinical studies have also shown that PRF enhances osseointegration in the early phase. [9] Enrichment of PRF has been accomplished in the past using Ascorbic acid to gain gingival tissue and radiographic defect fill in intrabony defects in periodontitis patients. Ascorbic acid (AA) is an effective antioxidant which has a definitive effect on periodontium. AA stimulates self-renewal and differentiation of periodontal progenitor and/ or stem cells, prevents aging of cells and enhances expression of multipotency biomarkers. [6] The 2017 World Workshop on the Classification of Periodontal and Peri-Implant Diseases and Conditions defines the “periodontal phenotype” as a combination of mucosal thickness, keratinized tissue width and bone morphotype.

Hence, in our study, we have assessed a newer variant of PRF membrane, infusing it with Ascorbic acid and compared it to L-PRF membrane to assess for improvement in wound healing and periodontal phenotype around immediate implants. No study in our knowledge has assessed efficacy of AA-PRF around immediate implants. Although, there was a non-significant difference for the median wound healing index scores between the L-PRF and AA-PRF groups but there was an improved wound healing in both groups at day 14 from day 7. Similar results were obtained in a study conducted by *Arora et al* [10] where they compared immediate implant placement with or without PRF placement and concluded that early wound closure was observed in group with PRF membrane. Another study by *Xiao Li et al* [11] checked for role of vitamin C in implant sites for healing after treatment with bone grafts and concluded that augmentation with Vitamin C improved postoperative healing at day 7 and day 14.

The mean keratinized tissue width at 3 months for L-PRF and AA-PRF group did not show significant difference ($p>0.05$). However, the keratinized tissue width gain from baseline to 3 months was statistically significant ($p<0.05$) in favour of the AA-PRF group. Similar results were obtained by *Zeinab Al-Diasty et al* [12] and *Moeintaghavi et al* [13] in their studies, where they concluded that PRF membrane had a role to play in increasing the keratinized mucosa width around implants around 3mm from baseline to 3 months. The mean Mucosal Thickness from baseline to 3 months for the L-PRF and AA-PRF did not show any significant difference ($p>0.05$). Our results were similar to a case series by *da Silva Lima et al* [14] where they used three PRF membranes with immediate implant placement and assessed peri-implant mucosal thickness as their primary outcome. But another study by *Soni et al* [15] which checked for efficacy of L-PRF in immediate implant placement and demonstrated no benefit of L-PRF in terms of peri-implant tissue thickness.

The mean crestal bone levels at 3 months for the L-PRF and AA-PRF did not show significant difference ($p>0.05$). There are no studies evaluating effect of AA-PRF on the peri-implant bone levels. A study by *Elbehwashy et al* [6] who assessed the radiographic effects of AA-PRF versus PRF alone in intra-osseous defects in stage-III periodontitis patients concluded that AA-PRF resulted in significant radiographic defect fill at 6 months. Studies by *Medikeri et al* [16] and *Chauhan et al* [17] where they evaluated crestal bone level around immediate implants with and without PRF found no statistically significant difference from baseline to 12 months and 9 months respectively, when compared between both groups. These results were consistent with our study.

To the best of our knowledge, our study is the first to investigate the effect of Ascorbic acid with PRF membrane in improving the quality of tissue around implants. Limitations of our study include relatively small sample size. A randomized trial on larger population size is needed to further introspect or validate the findings of this study. Longer Follow ups longer than 3 months need to be recorded to assess bone changes. A follow up period of at least 6 months to 1 year are required to observe complete soft and hard tissue changes.

CONCLUSION

Within the limitations of the current study, it can be concluded that although both L-PRF and AA-PRF membranes showed improvements in terms of clinical and radiographic parameters at 3 months interval post-surgically, the PRF enriched with Ascorbic Acid supplement further improved the quality of peri-implant tissues. The results emphasize on a positive role of local enhancement of Ascorbic acid in implant sites. Having said that, further clinical and histological examinations with longer follow-up terms and more sample pools are required to establish this as a potent treatment modality.

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